

Histopathological Alterations in The Intestine of Marine Fish *Chiloscyllium plagiosum* (Anonymous (Bennett), 1830) Due to *Phyllobothrium*

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Abstract

The studies of histopathological alterations in the intestine of *Chiloscyllium plagiosum* (Anonymous (Bennett), 1830) with infection of helminthic parasite *Phyllobothrium* from At Alibag coast, Dist Raigad (M. S) India in the period of June 2018 to May 2019. This parasite caused significant histopathological alterations in the *Chiloscyllium plagiosum* marine water fish intestine, The severe infection was evidenced by the total eruption of villi from the mucous membrane which resulted to a major disruption of the structural organization of the intestine which might have a profound influence on the nutrition and digestion process of the fish.

The present paper deals with the histopathological alterations showed the intestine of marine water fish *Chiloscyllium plagiosum* infected with helminthic parasite *Phyllobothrium*

Keywords: Marine fish, *Chiloscyllium plagiosum* Infected Intestine, Cestode *Phyllobothrium*

Introduction:

Histopathology is the microscopic study of tissues affected by disease the procedure adopted for that preparation of material for such studies are known as Histological or Histopathological techniques. The digestive tract of many fish has been shown to be a favourite environment for the establishment and growth of pathogenic organisms. Endoparasites helminth often includes inflammation and modification of the structures and function of local tissues (Castro, 1992). According to Sharkey (1992), the inflammations consist of a complex series of homeostatic mechanism involving the immune, nervous and circulatory system in response to tissues injury or infection. There are several published records on the essential role of enteric immune cells in inflammatory processes caused by parasitic Helminthes (Fairweather, 1997; Maifrino et al., 1999; Dezfuli et al., 2000a, 2002a, b, 2003b; Bosi et al., 2005).

Parasitic infections introduce an additional demand for the host resources (Poulin, 1998). Infections can be costly for the host through competition with the parasite over limited resources and ultimately through energy depletion caused by the parasite (Coops & Holmes, 1996), which might have an impact on the decision making and optimal resources allocation pattern of the host. The host could therefore benefit from parasite resistance by decreasing the effect of parasite or avoiding parasites. However, it has been generating trade off with life history traits (Sand land & Minchella, 2003). Several studies on the effect of intestinal parasites have shown that the main detrimental consequences for the host species are localised at the site of infection (Hoste, 2001).

Material & Methods

Marine fish *Chiloscyllium plagiosum* (Anonymous (Bennett), 1830) were brought to the local laboratory alive and sacrificed just before examination. During the parasitological examination, the intestines were cut open and examined under stereomicroscope to see the degree of infection. The tapeworms were collected, placed in saline solution, freed from the adhering mucus by gentle shaking, they were flattened, processed and stained for morphological studies and were identified as *Phyllobothrium vatsalabaiae n. sp.* within short time 2 to 3 cm long pieces of proximal intestinal segments containing tapeworms were fix in Bouin's solution for 24 hrs, as the tissue undergoes autolysis rapidly after death and rapid fixation is essential.

The fixed material was transferred and processed through ascending grades of alcohol, dried in a wax miscible agent and impregnated in wax (M. P. 58°-60°C). Sectioning was carried out on a rotary microtome at 6µm. Sections were floated on warm water at 48°C and mounted on chemically cleaned slides coated with egg albumin. The mounted, unstained sections were dewaxed in three stages of xylene at 1 minute each and stained with most widely used standard haematoxylin and eosin stain, staining was carried out using haematoxylin and eosin staining technique (Bullock, 1978). This stained is often sufficient for identification of larger parasites such as Helminthes, in this method the nuclei of cells are stained by the haematoxylin; the cytoplasm is coloured by the eosin. Stained mounted sections were examined under light microscope for good ones that were selected for photomicrography.

Result & Discussion:

Histopathology of *Phyllobothrium vatsalabaiæ* n.sp. infection of the intestine *Chiloscyllium plagiosum* (Anonymous (Bennett), 1830). The selected slides were observed under microscope and reveal that it causes much damage to the host intestine by invading in the mucosa layer. It is very clearly seen parasite in the transverse section of the intestine. The worm *Phyllobothrium vatsalabaiæ* n.sp. is having nonpenetrative type of scolex, further it was observed that parasite is easily floating near the villi in lumen of intestine. The worm is able to reach the intestine and is adhered to it. Due to favourable condition for the parasites in the lumen of intestinal is freely floating to cause a disturbance in the absorption of food by piercing the intestinal tissue. The host intestine is rich in protein, carbohydrate and lipids and they are present in parasites, when have been accumulated by the active absorption of food by the help of teguments, from the nutritional rich environment. Thus, it can be concluded that the worm could be able to take nourishment from the host and tissue causing damage to the host's intestinal tissue.

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